

南京交通职业技术学院 & 吉扎克国立技术学院
Nanjing Vocational Institute of Transport Technology & Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

“交通领域科技创新与管理模式发展趋势”

"Technological Innovation and Management Model Development Trends in the Transportation Industry"

学术研讨会

Academic Seminar

2023年11月16日 南京 吉扎克

November 16, 2023 NANJING & JIZZAKH

目录

1、 Intelligent encryption method for wireless sensing signal of underwater vehicle	1
2、 Experimental study on anchoring performance of CFRP anchor	16
3、 Research on the Practical Training and Internship of Enterprises with Deep Integration of Industry and Education in Higher Vocational Colleges---Taking the Logistics Management Major of Nanjing Vocational Institute of Transport Technology as an Example	23
4、 Research on Navigation Accuracy of Unmanned Surface Vessel Based on Federated Kalman Filtering Algorithm	37
5、 Practice and Application of Slip Construction Method for Steel-concrete Composite Beam Section	41
6、 Research on the Technology of Utilizing Braking Energy of Urban Rail Transit Trains	49
7、 Analysis on the Application and Development Trends of New Intelligent Traffic Technologies	69
8、 Demand-oriented Eco-design strategy for electrical and electronic products	81
9、 Effect Of Air Filter Pollution On Engine Indicators	119
10、 Assessment Of The Quality Of Public Transport Service	124
11、 Role Of Transport Logistics In The Development Of Industry	132
12、 Information System In The Function OF Railway Traffic Management	138
13、 ACTive ANd PASSive CAR Safety Systems	147
14、 Factors Of Using Logistics Services In The Field Of Transport And Logistics	160
15、 Development Of An Experimental Copy Of A Machine That Plucks Cotton	164
16、 Analysis Of Vehicle Safety Test Methods	170
17、 Special Features Of Small-sized Vegetable Tractors	182
18、 Influence Of Particles Formed Resulting From Wear Of Automobile Brake Mechanisms On Human Health	186
19、 Logistic Methods Of Analysis And Assortment Managementretail Trade Enterprises	196
20、 Determining The Peak Period Of Traffic Intensity At Anintersection	205
21、 Analysis Of Problems Of Population Mobility And Prospects Of Development	213
22、 Priority Systems Of Public Transportation At Intersections	222

PRIORITY SYSTEMS OF PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION AT INTERSECTIONS

Pulatov Sukhrobjon Golibjon ugli

suxrobpulatov7777@gmail.com

Jizzakh polytechnic institute, Assistant teacher

Baratov Ilhomjon Iskandar ugli

ilhomlogist07@gmail.com

Jizzakh polytechnic institute, Assistant teacher

Abstract: This article is about the traffic of public transport at central city intersections and the technologies used in their priority. In addition, scientifically based suggestions on ensuring the priority and safety of traffic in the organization of public transport at intersections and recommendations on its implementation are given..

Keywords: bus priority systems, non-adaptive bus priority systems, dedicated bus lane.

Non-adaptive bus prioritization involves passive measures that prioritize buses at some points in the network. These are bus lanes. In this case, conflicts of buses with other vehicles do not occur, as a result, speed and safety are improved.

Bus routes can be permanent or part-time. It is usually used during the morning rush hour, but can also be used as a normal route during the rest of the day.

We use a bus route in some part of the traffic route and select one of the bus routes in the city for the purpose of analyzing it. We make this selection based on requirements such as high traffic flow and high number of buses. The intersection of Sh.Rashidov Street and Baynalminalchilar Street in the center of Jizzakh city was chosen. (Fig. 1))

Figure 1. The intersection of Sharof Rashidov street with Baynalminalchilar streets.

Bus route 212, which is used by many passengers, passing through this street, was chosen. GPS data of bus route 212 on February 15, 2023 was obtained for the analysis of traffic indicators.

We will analyze 2 routes of bus traffic in the evening rush hour and in normal time. We designate Jizzakh Shahar Kok bazar Auto Station as A, Ushtepa center as B. The travel time of bus route 212 from A to B is 1 hour and 59 minutes.

At normal time, the bus started from A at 5:54:17 and reached B at 6:52:43. The bus covered the distance in 0:58:26 and arrived on time.

The average speed of the bus during movement was equal to $v_m = \frac{v_1 + v_2 + \dots + v_n}{n} = 26,6 \frac{km}{h}$ [Diagram 1].

Diagram 1. Variation of velocity with time in normal time.

During heavy traffic, Bus 212 started at 17:45:00 and arrived at the last bus stop at 19:17:08. It took 1:32:08 to cover the course and was half an hour behind schedule.

The average speed during rush hour was equal to $v_{or} = \frac{v_1+v_2+..v_n}{n} =$

18,3 km/h. [diagram 2]

Diagram 2. Change in speed over time during rush hour.

Using GPS data, we will consider the section between the intersection of Sh Rashidov Street and Baynalminalchilar Street, with and without heavy traffic. We find the times of arrival and departure of the bus to the specified section, and find the average speed during this period for both cases.

The bus traveled the studied road with an average speed of 25.9 km/h in normal times and 16.2 km/h in heavy traffic. We present all the average speeds in one graph. [Diagram 3]

Diagram 3. Average speed changes.

If we can conclude from the graph, the average speed of the studied section in normal time is almost equal to the average speed of the route, and in the time of heavy traffic, the average speed of both the route and the studied section is lower. For this reason, it is correct to use the bus lane only at peak times, and at other times the road should be in general use.

In other cities where there is a bus lane, the following signs are used [Figure 2].

Figure 2. In other cities where there is a bus lane, the following signs are used.

The figure shows that motorcycles, bicycles and taxis are allowed to use the bus lane. The times below are bus lane operating times, during which you should not drive through the bus lane.

Special traffic lights are required to ensure the priority of buses even at the traffic lights in the lanes reserved for buses. That is, giving more green time to other vehicles moving in the same direction, for example, giving buses the green phase a few seconds before giving to other vehicles and allowing them to pass in front of traffic. In addition, it is useful to use bus lanes when phase-to-phase coordination (green waves) is performed at consecutive traffic lights. A green wave occurs when a sequence of traffic lights (usually three or more) are coordinated to provide a continuous flow of vehicles through multiple intersections in one main direction.

Any vehicle traveling on a green wave (at an approximate speed decided by traffic engineers) sees green lights and does not stop at intersections. This allows for higher vehicle loads and reduces noise and energy consumption (because less acceleration and braking is required).

In 2011, a green wave implementation study was modeled in a suburb of Manchester (Chorlton-cum-Hardy) at night. With the help of the results, the following opportunities were achieved:

- Reduce CO₂, NO_x and PM₁₀ emissions from traffic.
- Reduction of fuel consumption of motor vehicles.
- Use on roads crossed by other green waves.
- Controlling traffic speed in urban areas.
- Reduce energy consumption.

Sometimes green waves are used to facilitate cycling. Used for the flow of cyclists in Copenhagen, Amsterdam, San Francisco. The green wave on Copenhagen's Norrebrogade main street helped 30,000 cyclists maintain a speed of 19.3 km/h for 2.5 kilometers. In Amsterdam, cyclists will be able to travel at a speed of 15 to 18 km/h without stopping at a red light. Public transport can also benefit, and cars can travel a little slower.

Frederiksberg, part of the Danish capital Copenhagen, has implemented a green wave for emergency vehicles to improve public services.

In Germany, the term "green wave" was also used for rail traffic for several years starting in the 1960s..

References

1. Development the public transport priority with bus rapid transit (brt) on intersections roads in uzbekistan

Rakhmatov utkirjon, sotvoldiev hasanboy, ilhomov sardor, pulatov sukhrobjon

2. Обслуживание Специальных Транспортных Средств, Используемых В Производстве, И Его Дополнительные Воздействия

Сардор илхомов, сухробжон пулатов

3. Transport vositalari xavfsizligini takomillashtirish

Dots. Abdunazarov jamshid nurmuhammatovich, mag. Valiyev muhammadali komiljon o'g'li, mag. Pulatov suxrobjon g'olibjon o'g'li, baratov ilhomjon "ilmiy-tadqiqotlar, innovatsiyalar va ilmiy-pedagogik kadrlar tayyorlash bo'limi" muhandisi

4. A bus rapid transit line case study: istanbul's metrobus system

Anil yazici 1, herbert s. Levinson 2, mustafa ilicali 3, nilgün camkesen 4, camille kamga